

The challenges that faced by autism people in the world in different domains

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Abstract:

One of the most prevalent disorders today is autism. It is one of the most difficult disorders to treat. People with autism require special care. because they encounter numerous difficulties during their lives. In the early months, it might be challenging to diagnose autism, but as the child gets older, it is easier since the symptoms become extremely obvious via the actions of the child. Patients with autism become cut off from the outside world. They enjoy sitting by themselves and not interacting with anyone or attempting to start a conversation, no matter how simple. Due to his inability to express his wants in the same way as other kids, the youngster will be difficult for parents to grasp. The most typical signs include tiptoeing, ignoring danger sensitivity to sounds, etc. The most challenging aspect of autism is how exhausting it is for both the autistic person and those close to him, such as family and friends. They occasionally exhibit peculiar behavior, so people must exercise patience while dealing with them. However, this does not give people the right to treat them poorly because psychological factors have a significant impact on them. Autism comes in a variety of grades. For instance, while some people's symptoms are straightforward, others have more obvious ones. Despite being a congenital disorder, research have suggested that autism may be acquired. People with autism are known to experience a variety of issues. Therefore, we decided to depict all the difficulties that they would encounter when We seek a suitable and acceptable resolution for them, their families, and their way of life. Since many people don't know much about autism, this study will serve as a resource for them as they further their own education.

Keywords: Autism, Challenges, Communication, Behavior, Symptoms, ASD.